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МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ В ШКОЛАХ И КОЛЛЕДЖАХ

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METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT SCHOOLS AND COLLEGES

Аннотация:

Методика обучения иностранным языкам является практическим применением сравнительного языкознания. В настоящее время, когда в образовании происходят коренные изменения, когда радикально пересматриваются содержание и методы обучения, уместно вернуться к рассмотрению истории методики обучения иностранным языкам и основных тенденций ее развития. Наиболее полное определение методики звучит так: «Методика обучения — это наука, изучающая цели и содержание, закономерности, средства, приемы, методы и системы обучения, а также изучающая процессы обучения и воспитания на материале иностранного языка».

В начале XX века пропагандировался прямой метод. Считалось, что в основе этого метода лежит правильный принцип — ассоциирование иностранных слов с самими объектами. Это был метод естественного изучения иностранного языка, который является наиболее экономичным, наиболее быстрым для достижения цели. Кроме того, для многих методистов и преподавателей прямой метод был чем-то новым, привлекательным, и они искренне верили в его эффективность. Позже сформировался сравнительный метод обучения иностранным языкам, получивший свое название от того, что изучение иностранного языка предполагается на основе его сопоставления с родным языком. А при сочетании прямого и сравнительного методов родился смешанный метод. В зависимости от того, какие принципы в нем преобладают, он может быть ближе либо к прямому, либо к сравнительному методу. Со временем менялись не только цели обучения иностранному языку и требования к владению им. Методика обучения иностранному языку оказалась в кризисной ситуации. Кризисная ситуация всегда требует радикального поворота. Так, в условиях недостатка плодотворных идей был осуществлен переход к коммуникативному обучению. Кризис возродил активный методический поиск, что способствовало разработке современных методических концепций обучения иностранным языкам: коммуникативной, интенсивной, деятельностной и других. В настоящее время определяющую роль играют коммуникативно-ориентированные методы, в основе которых лежит общение и творчество учащихся.

Abstract.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is a practical application of comparative linguistics. At present, when fundamental changes are taking place in education, when the content and methods of teaching are being radically revised, it is appropriate to return to the consideration of the history of foreign language teaching methods and the main trends in its development. The most complete definition of methodology is: "Teaching methodology is a science that studies the goals and content, patterns, means, techniques, methods and systems of teaching, and also studies the processes of learning and education using the material of a foreign language."

At the beginning of the 20th century, the direct method was promoted. It was believed that this method was based on the correct principle - associating foreign words with the objects themselves. It was a method of natural study of a foreign language, which is the most economical, the fastest to achieve the goal. In addition, for many methodologists and teachers, the direct method was something new, attractive, and they sincerely believed in its effectiveness. Later, a comparative method of teaching foreign languages was formed, which received its name from the fact that the study of a foreign language is supposed to be based on its comparison with the native language.

And with the combination of direct and comparative methods, a mixed method was born. Depending on which principles prevail in it, it can be closer to either the direct or the comparative method. Over time, not only the goals of teaching a foreign language and the requirements for proficiency in it changed. The methodology of teaching a foreign language found itself in a crisis situation. A crisis situation always requires a radical turn. Thus, in the conditions of a lack of fruitful ideas, a transition to communicative teaching was made. The crisis revived an active methodological search, which contributed to the development of modern methodological concepts of teaching foreign languages: communicative, intensive, activity-based and others. At present,

communication-oriented methods, which are based on communication and creativity of students, play a decisive role.

Ключевые слова: обучение иностранному языку, методы, сравнение, учитель, ученик, современный
Key words: teaching a foreign language, methods, comparison, teacher, student, modern

Introduction. Methods of teaching foreign languages should develop further, since stagnation is destructive for any science. Comparison of modern teaching methods plays an important role, since new methods appear on their basis and it would be desirable that they do not have those disadvantages and shortcomings that are inherent in modern methods. Comparative characteristics are also important for choosing a job as a teacher. With such a variety, it is very difficult to make a choice without knowing the features and specifics of the methods. The functions of the teacher in the educational process have changed significantly. The teacher-mentor, the teacher-dictator have been replaced by the teacher-observer, the teacher-mediator, the teacher-"pacifier" and "leader". Although the personality of the teacher in this case fades into the background, its influence on the audience does not decrease, but, on the contrary, increases.

The actuality of the our research work lies in the fact that at the current stage of development of teaching foreign languages, the choice of teaching method is based on the characteristics of the team in which it will be used; it is necessary to take into account the personal characteristics of the students, their age, interests, level of training, the period during which the training will take place, as well as the technical equipment of the educational institution.

The purpose of this work is to identify the most effective methods in teaching a foreign language from existing modern methods of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools and colleges.

To achieve these goals, **the following tasks** are solved in the work:

- to consider existing modern methods of teaching foreign languages in secondary schools and colleges.
- to show similar and distinctive features, positive and negative sides of each method.
- to determine general methodological principles of organizing the teaching of foreign languages in secondary schools and colleges.
- to study the concept of communicative competence.
- to prove the advantage of active communication in English lessons in secondary schools and colleges.

The object of the study is the process of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools and colleges. **The subject of the study** is modern methods of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools and colleges.

In our study, we proceed from the **hypothesis**: the use of special methods contributes to the formation of communicative competence of students. **The novelty of the work** lies in the consideration of new, modern methods of teaching English, as well as in the combination of material. **The practical value of this work** is that its results can be used by English teachers in secondary schools, as well as by future specialists – students majoring in "Foreign Language" in practical

classes on the subject "Methodology of Teaching Foreign Languages". **The methods of scientific research** used in the work: - analysis of scientific literature, observation of students in the process of teaching English in secondary schools and colleges.

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages

The advancement of foreign language culture as a goal of education gave rise to the question of the need to create a new methodological system that could ensure the achievement of this goal in the most effective and rational way. The logic of developing the communicative methodology led to the final advancement of foreign language culture as the goal of teaching foreign languages in secondary schools and colleges. And such a system can only be built on a communicative basis.

In addition, as the practice of using the communicative methodology has shown, it ensures not only the acquisition of a foreign language as a means of communication, but also the development of comprehensive personal qualities of students. The communicative method was the basis for the creation of English language textbooks in secondary schools. In the last two decades, a trend known as projectivity has been forming in education. This concept was formulated in the context of the program for the restructuring of education proposed in the late 1970s by the Royal College of Art in Great Britain. It is closely connected with the project culture, which arose as a result of the unification of the humanitarian-artistic and scientific-technical directions in education. Project culture is, as it were, the general formula in which the art of planning, invention, creation, execution and design is realized and which is defined as design.

By mastering the design culture, the student learns to think creatively, independently planning his actions, predicting possible options, solutions to the problems facing him, implementing the tools and methods of work he has learned. The design culture is now included in many areas of educational practice in the form of project methods and project teaching methods. The project method is also actively included in teaching foreign languages. A striking example of the application of the project method is the textbook "Project English", published in 1985 by Oxford University Press. The author of the course is T. Hutchinson, a specialist in the field of communicative teaching of grammar.

Currently, intensive teaching of foreign languages is implemented in various developing, newly created and existing methodological systems. This is due to the diversity of specific goals of teaching a foreign language to various contingents of students, as well as the diversity of learning conditions (the schedule of teaching hours, their number, the size of the study group).

Methodological principles of modern methods of teaching foreign languages

In the course of the development of foreign language teaching methods, crises of deficit and "overproduction" of ideas necessary for the formation of a new methodological direction alternated. For example, the transition to communicative teaching was carried out in conditions of an obvious shortage of fruitful and truly new ideas. The crisis gave rise to an active methodological search, which contributed to the development of modern methodological concepts of teaching foreign languages: communicative, activity-based, etc.

In order to understand what modern methods of teaching English are based on, it is necessary to examine in detail the methodological principles that underlie these methods. The structure of the communicative method includes cognitive, developmental and educational aspects that are aimed at educating the student. Taking this into account and the content of the concept of "communicativeness", as well as the versatility of the teaching system, we can formulate the following methodological principles of the communicative method:

The principle of mastering all aspects of foreign language culture through communication. Foreign language culture here means everything that the process of mastering a foreign language can bring to students in the educational, cognitive, developmental and upbringing aspects [4, p.31]. The communicative method was the first to put forward the position that communication should be taught only through communication. In this case, communication can be used as a channel for education, knowledge and development. Communication is a social process in which there is an exchange of activities, experiences embodied in material and spiritual culture. In communication, emotional and rational interaction of people and influence on each other is carried out. It is communication that is the most important condition for proper education. Thus, communication performs the functions of training, cognition and development and education in the communicative teaching method. The process of teaching foreign language communication is a model of the process of real communication according to the main parameters: motivation, purposefulness, informativeness of the communication process, novelty, situationality, functionality, the nature of interaction of communicants and the system of speech means. Due to this, learning conditions are created that are adequate to real ones, which ensures successful acquisition of skills and their use in real communication conditions.

The principle of interrelated teaching of aspects of foreign language culture. The complex nature of foreign language culture is manifested in the unity and interrelation of its educational, cognitive, upbringing and developmental aspects. Each of these aspects, in a practical sense, is equivalent. But true mastery of one is possible only under the condition of proper mastery of the others. In this regard, any type of work, any exercise in the educational process, integrates all four aspects of foreign language culture and is assessed depending on the presence of these aspects in them. This principle concerns not only inter-*aspect*

relationships, but also intra-*aspect* relationships. For example, it assumes the interconnection and interdependence of all four types of speech activity (reading, speaking, listening and writing) within the educational process. The need for interconnected learning is justified by the learning pattern, according to which mastery occurs more successfully, the more analyzers participate in it. Interconnectedness is present not only in the learning process, but also in individual exercises specially developed within the framework of this methodology.

The principle of modeling the content of aspects of foreign language culture. The volume of regional, linguistic and lingua-regional knowledge of reality cannot be fully assimilated within the framework of a school course, therefore it is necessary to build a model of the content of the object of cognition, that is, to select, depending on the purpose of training and the content of the course, that volume of the specified knowledge that will be sufficient to present the culture of the country and the language system. At the same time, it is also necessary to take into account the cognitive needs of individual students associated with their individual interests, etc. Certain frameworks of the training system and its final tasks require, for methodological purposes, the creation of a model of the content of development, that is, a certain minimum that is necessary to solve the problems facing the subject.

The principle of managing the educational process based on its quantization and programming. Any system of training presupposes quantization of all components of the training process (goals, means, material, etc.). Without quantization, the goals will be incorrect, the material will be indigestible, the conditions will be suboptimal, and the means will be inadequate. In other words, the systematic nature of training will be impossible, including its controllability and effectiveness.

The principle of systematicity in the organization of teaching foreign languages. This principle means that the communicative system of teaching is built in a reverse way: first, the final product (goal) is outlined, and then the tasks that can lead to this result are determined. This takes place within the entire course, each year, a cycle of lessons and one lesson and concerns all aspects. This approach ensures systematicity in teaching with all its inherent qualities: integrity, hierarchy, purposefulness. The systematic nature of training is built taking into account the patterns of students' mastery of each of its aspects. All training in organizational terms is built on the basis of the rules of cyclicity and concentricity. Cyclicity is manifested in the fact that a certain amount of material is learned within a cycle of lessons, each of which includes a certain number of lessons. Any cycle is built on the basis of the stage-by-stage development of a particular skill and ability in each type of speech activity. The systemic nature is manifested in the fact that the proposed system includes not only the foreign language teacher and the student, but also his parents, teachers of other subjects. Interdisciplinary connections are used as a means of additional motivation for those students who are not interested in a foreign language.

Distinctive features of modern methods

Many modern methods are communication-oriented, and one of their most important goals is teaching communication and mastery of speech means. Each of the methods uses different means, methods and principles. That is, each of the methods has distinctive specific features. The very first specific feature of the communicative methodology is that the goal of teaching is not mastering a foreign language, but a "foreign language culture", which includes cognitive, educational, developmental and educational aspects. These aspects include familiarization and study of not only the linguistic and grammatical system of the language, but also its culture, its relationship with the native culture, as well as the structure of the foreign language, its character, features, similarities and differences with the native language. The second specific feature of the communicative method is mastering all aspects of foreign language culture through communication. It was the communicative method that first put forward the position that communication should be taught only through communication, which has become one of the characteristic features of modern methods. In the communicative method of teaching, communication performs the functions of learning, cognition, development and education "Thus, task-based language teaching and telecollaboration work well together to improve language fluency and accuracy while also developing crosscultural awareness and 21st-century abilities that equip students for the needs of a globalized society. The integration of telecollaborative projects and task-based learning is a strategy that shows promise in fostering efficient language acquisition as educators continue to investigate novel approaches to language instruction" [1, p174].

The communicative method also includes mastering non-verbal means of communication: such as gestures, facial expressions, postures, distance, which is an additional factor in memorizing lexical and any other material.

A specific feature of the communicative method is also the use of conditional speech exercises, that is, exercises that are based on full or partial repetition of the teacher's lines. As knowledge and skills are acquired, the nature of conditional speech exercises becomes more and more complex, until the need for them is exhausted, when the statements of the students do not become independent and meaningful. Thus, from all of the above it is clear that many specific features that first appeared in the communicative concept were then adopted by other communicatively-oriented methods and are successfully used by them. But at the same time they differ in many ways from this concept and have their own features, inherent only to them.

The effectiveness of the project-based methodology is largely ensured by the intellectual and emotional content of the topics included in the training. It should also be noted that they gradually become more complex. But the distinctive feature of the topics is their concreteness. From the very beginning of training, it is assumed that students will participate in meaningful

and complex communication, without the simplification and primitivism that are usually characteristic of textbooks for beginners in learning a foreign language. Another distinctive feature of the project-based methodology is a special form of organizing the communicative and cognitive activity of students in the form of a project. This is where the name of the methodology actually came from.

A project, as mentioned earlier, is an independent work carried out by the student, in which verbal communication is woven into the intellectual and emotional context of another activity.

The novelty of the approach is that students are given the opportunity to construct the content of communication themselves, starting from the first lesson. There are few texts as such in the course; they are reproduced in the process of students working on projects proposed by the authors.

Each project is related to a specific topic and is developed over a certain period of time. The topic has a clear structure, is divided into subtopics, each of which ends with an assignment for the project work. A particularly important feature is that students have the opportunity to talk about their thoughts and plans. Working on a project creates a solid language base. Also specific is the division of skills into two types: the skills of a language learner and the skills of a language user. Phonetic and lexical-grammatical exercises of a training nature are used to develop the first type of skills. These are exercises in imitation, substitution, expansion, transformation, restoration of individual phrases and texts. Their peculiarity is that they are given in an entertaining form: in the form of a text to test memory, attention; guessing games; puzzles, sometimes in the form of a phonogram.

Let's move on to the intensive method and consider its specifics. This method is based on the psychological term "suggestion". This is the first specific feature of the intensive method. The use of suggestion allows to bypass or remove various kinds of psychological barriers in students in the following way. The teacher conducts classes taking into account psychological factors, emotional impact, using logical forms of training. He also uses various types of art (music, painting, elements of theater) in classes, with the purpose of emotional impact on students. However, suggestopedic teaching presupposes a certain concentration of study hours. At the senior stages, for example, it is advisable to allocate six hours a week at the expense of the school component of the curriculum, they should be divided into three, two hours each. If necessary, the number of hours can be reduced to three. Also, a specific feature of the intensive method is that suggestopedics widely relies on the position on the different functions of the two hemispheres of the brain. The inclusion of emotional factors in teaching a foreign language significantly activates the process of assimilation, opening up new prospects in the development of foreign language teaching methods.

Another distinctive factor is the active use of role-playing games. The specificity of intensive training is that educational communication preserves all the social and psychological processes of communication. Role-

playing communication is simultaneously a game, and educational, and speech activity. But at the same time, if from the position of students, role-playing communication is a game activity or natural communication, when the motive is not in the content of the activity, but outside of it, then from the position of the teacher, role-playing communication is a form of organizing the educational process. According to L.G. Denisova, [5, p.11] the main effective moments of the interactive methodology of teaching foreign languages are:

- creation of strong immediate motivation for learning, carried out in informal communication and motivation for communication close to real;

- high and immediate effectiveness of learning: already on the second day of classes, students communicate in the studied foreign language, using speech cliches embedded in the main educational text - remember, the text of the polylogue is introduced on the first day of classes;

- presentation and assimilation of a large number of speech, lexical and grammatical units; in one presentation, 150-200 new words, 30-50 speech cliches and several typical grammatical phenomena are introduced and assimilated.

This is also, undoubtedly, a specific feature. All of the above are the features of the intensive method, which to a greater extent ensure its effectiveness. These specific moments are almost completely different from the two previous methods. Only in one thing, perhaps, are they similar. All three methods consider collective work in a positive emotional atmosphere a necessary condition for successful learning. At the same time, the intensive method pays more attention to such types of activity as speaking and listening.

Common features in modern methods

At present, the goal of teaching English is formulated as follows: to teach students to communicate in English. But with this goal set, it becomes an end in itself. The goal of education is much broader than acquiring certain skills and abilities, and the potential of the subject "English" is much broader. Therefore, the goal of teaching English at the moment can be formulated as follows: to teach students not only to participate in communication in English, but also to actively participate in the formation and development of the student's personality.

Based on this, most modern methods of teaching English are based on the principle of active communication. Active communication involves building learning as a model of the communication process. In order to give learning the main features of the communication process, firstly, it is necessary to switch to personal communication with students (the principle of individualization in the communicative method, the principle of personality-oriented thinking in the intensive method, etc.), due to which a normal psychological climate is formed in working with the audience. Secondly, to solve this problem, it is necessary to use all methods of communication - interactive, when the teacher interacts with students on the basis of some activity, in addition to the educational one, perceptive, when there is a perception of each

other as individuals, bypassing the statuses of teacher and student, informational, when the student and teacher exchange their thoughts, feelings, and not words and grammatical structures. And the third necessary condition is the creation of communicative motivation - a need that encourages students to participate in communication in order to change the relationship with the interlocutor. Communication should be structured in such a way that gradual mastery of speech material occurs. The motivation for communication can be various incentives. When working with the project method, this is work on joint projects. The same incentive is used in the intensive method. Often, situations used during training are problematic. These situations should contribute to the formation of different opinions among students and not provide an unambiguous solution. Discussion of such situations allows different opinions to collide, causes the need to defend one's point of view, that is, the need to communicate in a foreign language. The use of problem situations also has another positive side, as it makes it possible to solve educational tasks, since it is possible to educate an active personality only by discussing situations based on genuine values.

In addition, collective joint activity is widely used in almost all methods. The tendency to replace individual work with group work has been developing for a long time. Collective work greatly activates the team. The formation of skills and abilities occurs in the system of collective actions, which contribute to the internal mobilization of the capabilities of each student. Forms of collective interaction are easily implemented in classes. This is work in pairs, three, in microgroups and in full groups. It should also be noted that role communication, constantly interacting with personal communication, is its prerequisite and condition. Situations of role communication, in which the skills and abilities of foreign language communication are formed, ensure the transition to a higher level of communication.

The features of intensive methods of teaching English are becoming increasingly widespread in foreign language teaching methods. For example, multifunctional exercises. It is necessary to remember that multifunctionality is inherent and should be characteristic of all speech exercises in the existing teaching practice. After all, several types of activity are involved: listening, speaking and certain grammatical knowledge. The same is true of conventional speech exercises, which were once a characteristic feature of the commutative method. Now they are also used in the interactive method.

The main direction of modern foreign language teaching

There are always certain relationships between potential participants in communication. At some point, one of them has a need to make contact, a need related to one or another aspect of human life. This may be a need for something specific; then communication will become an auxiliary activity, a means of satisfying the need. But this may also be a need for communication itself, then communication is an independent activity. The question arises: is it possible to organize training

so that communication training takes place in the conditions of communication, i.e. in adequate conditions? Yes, it is possible. This is what communicativeness serves. How does it manifest itself?

Firstly, in taking into account the individuality of each student. After all, each person differs from another in their natural abilities, and the ability to carry out educational and speech activities, and their characteristics as an individual: personal experience, a set of certain feelings and emotions, their interests, their position in the class.

Secondly, communicativeness is manifested in the speech orientation of the learning process. It consists in the fact that the path to practical mastery of speaking as a means of communication lies through the practical use of the language itself. First of all, this concerns exercises. After all, it is in them that the necessary conditions for learning are created. The more an exercise resembles real communication, the more useful it is.

Thirdly, communicativeness is manifested in the functionality of learning. Every teacher knows the fact that students, knowing words, being able to form this or that grammatical form, are unable to use all this in the process of communication. The reason lies in the teaching strategy, according to which words are first learned by heart, and the grammatical form is "trained" in isolation from speech functions, and then their use in speaking is organized. As a result, the word or grammatical form is not associated with the speech task (function) and then, when the speaker needs to perform this function in communication, it is not recalled from memory.

Teaching speech skills

In modern methodology, more and more attention is paid to the idea of considering communication in the broad context of human activity, such as: knowledge, mastery of spiritual values, work, study, play. In any communication situation there is a speaker or writer, listener or reader. Hence the identification of the main types of speech activity: productive (speaking, writing, associated with sending a message) and receptive (listening and reading, associated with receiving it). Speaking and listening are oral types of speech activity, and writing and reading are written. The concept of listening includes the process of perception and understanding of spoken speech.

To create motivation for learning a foreign language and, in particular, in listening as learning something new about the language and the world, as active participation in communication, it is important to choose the right audio texts. Texts that are too difficult can cause disappointment in students, deprive them of faith in success, and texts that are too easy are also undesirable. The absence of a moment of overcoming difficulties makes the work uninteresting and unattractive, not to mention that it cannot be a developing factor in the process of learning a foreign language. The correct choice of the audio text topic is important from the point of view of the interests of college students of a particular age group. For primary school students, texts based on fairy tales and

entertaining stories about animals are accessible and interesting. High school students, as shown by research by Azerbaijanian methodologists, are interested in texts related to politics, technology, detectives. They listen with great interest to audio texts about love and friendship, about the life of peoples of other countries, about nature. Recently, the methodology has been talking about the importance of relying on the regional aspect when teaching a foreign language. If the texts for listening include information about the country of the language being studied, about the life and customs of its people, about holidays and traditions, then they develop the students' horizons and cultivate a sense of sympathy for other nations. "Creativity is the ability to make or otherwise bring into existence something new, whether a new solution to a problem, a new method or device, or a new artistic object or form" [3, p.125]. One of the effective means of creating motivation for learning a foreign language are texts devoted to youth problems. These problems have always existed and have always occupied young people, including high school students. However, only recently have they begun to be spoken about out loud, interesting radio and television programs, publications in the youth press have been devoted to them. A wider opportunity has appeared to discuss these problems with foreign peers using a foreign language. If a teacher includes audio texts in a lesson related to problems of youth leisure, modern music, informal associations, and problems of youth independence in modern life, he can be sure that such audio texts will not only be met with great interest by students, but will also entail a lively discussion. The main obstacle to perceiving speech by ear is the lack of a language environment, as a result of which the sound form of a word becomes a less powerful irritant than the graphic one, which leads to the failure to recognize words known to students. Students get used to perceiving information mainly through the visual channel. The teacher allows them to use the text when discussing and retelling it and actually read the proposed supports. In this case, the teacher himself slows down the development of auditory perception. Overcoming this difficulty is possible only if the teacher loads the students' auditory channel more, accustoming them to perceiving information by ear. The most effective way is when the teacher consciously leads students from favorable learning conditions to unfavorable ones, from the presence of verbal supports to their gradual removal.

In order to introduce students to reading in a foreign language, it is necessary, firstly, to stimulate the motivation for reading, and secondly, to ensure the success of its course with the help of appropriate tasks for exercises. These moments are interconnected and interdependent. The quality of texts plays an exceptional role in developing the motivation for reading. Their practical, general educational, and upbringing significance can be manifested only if they appeal to students. Many methodologists believe that "a text acquires meaning for a student when he can establish a certain relationship between his life experience and the content of this text."

Writing plays a major role in teaching a foreign language. At the beginning of learning, mastering graphics and spelling is the goal of mastering writing techniques in a new language for students. Later, writing is considered an important tool in learning a language: it helps to firmly assimilate language material (lexical, grammatical) and develop reading and speaking skills.

Information technology

Using computer technologies in teaching English. Computerization of the educational process is one of the most important tasks of modern education. It is associated with the development of the material and technical base of educational institutions, retraining of teachers, development of teaching methods, and the formation of a new culture of pedagogical work. The introduction of modern computer technologies, which are a fundamentally new means of teaching and a powerful tool for learning, requires the development of methods and organizational forms of teaching. At the current (initial) stage, the development of new methods is impossible without the joint work of the computer science teacher and subject teachers [6, p.18]. All methodological work of the group is based on the joint creative activity of teachers. This allows for the correct selection of computer technologies taking into account the specifics of subjects, their implementation in the process of teaching specific disciplines, and also to help teachers overcome psychological stress in the process of mastering skills in working with modern information technologies. The choice of integrating computer science and English was also determined by the fact that modern computer science vocabulary is based on English terminology. "While teaching four skills in classes, teachers integrate technology into their classes to teach receptive and productive skills. Thus, learners are exposed to target language discourse by native speakers thanks to films, and various video materials" [1, p.7]. Most software worldwide is English-language software products, and knowledge of English is necessary to master the tools of many information systems. Modern computer technologies are an integral part of multimedia technologies (from the English multi-many and media-environment). We consider these technologies as information technologies of training, integrating audiovisual information of any form (text, graphics, animation, etc.), implementing an interactive dialogue between the user and the system and a variety of forms of independent activity in processing information. "For that reason, teachers should guide their learners as to how to use such programs effectively. In addition, teachers should check the assignments and provide feedback regularly. Lack of feedback and monitoring of the learners' progress may demotivate them and stop using such software programs" [2, p.109]

The implementation of practical lessons, the educational process of a foreign language, confirmed that the school was motivated and prepared for the

process of teaching foreign languages through the use of computer technology. The use of the above-described new technologies was experimentally tested and introduced into the practice of our educational institution, which significantly affected the quality of teaching foreign languages, motivation for learning a foreign language.

Conclusion

The basis of the cultural approach in education is the following regularity: the development of a harmonious personality depends on the level of mastery of the basic humanitarian culture. Knowing other languages, a person gets the opportunity to cross the border of his native culture and meet other cultures. A dialogue of cultures occurs. A foreign language is an integral part of cultural education. The task of cultural education, including that projected onto a foreign language, is to create conditions in which the human personality can manifest itself in all its diversity and self-determination, conducting a dialogue within the horizon of culture. The personality is alive only in its address to others, in the perception of another in attention to another, in communication with another (or with oneself as the Other). This means that the personality exists where there is a dialogue. All methods, techniques and means of teaching a foreign language in the context of a dialogue of cultures are aimed at recognizing and understanding a new culture. In turn, such attitudes create a need to ensure such an organization of the educational process that would contribute to the formation and development of the learner's personality. The basis for teaching a foreign language in the context of a personal-activity approach should be not only and not so much the memorization of information, but the active participation of learners in acquiring knowledge, developing their ability for independent productive activity in a foreign language.

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